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A PHARMACOGNOSTICAL STUDY OF *BIDALI- Dioscorea pentaphylla* Linn.

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ABSTRACT

The ancient life science of India – Ayurveda, enumerates an extensive list of herbal medicines across its treatises, out of which many are not included in the Ayurvedic Pharmacopoeia of India. One among these plants is *Bidali*, and *Dioscorea pentaphylla* Linn. is the botanical source, belonging to Dioscoreaceae family. It is commonly known as Yam or Five leaf yam, which is used as staple food and to cure many health ailments by the tribals. The tubers of *Bidali- Dioscorea pentaphylla* Linn. was collected from Devarayana Durga, Savana Durga (Tumkuru), Perdooru (Udupi), and Badamanavaratekaval (Bengaluru). Pharmacognostical studies like Macroscopic, Microscopic, Organoleptic, Physico-chemical, Preliminary Qualitative Phytochemical Analysis and Quantitative Phytochemical Analysis were carried out. The results of preliminary qualitative phytochemical analysis revealed the presence of Alkaloids, Steroids, Carbohydrates, Starch, Protein, Tannins, Phenols, Flavonoids, Saponins. Quantitative phytochemical analysis showed the presence of Flavones and Saponins in higher concentration which indicates the therapeutic probabilities.

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INTRODUCTION

Ayurveda, the ancient life science of India, which aims to heal the illnesses of the distressed and maintain the health of the healthy individual^[1], enumerates an extensive list of herbal medicines, many of which are not included in the Ayurvedic Pharmacopoeia of India. One such drug is *Bidali*, which is considered as a variety of *Vidarikanda* (Indian Kudzu)- *Pueraria tuberosa* DC^[2-4]. It is botanically identified as *Dioscorea pentaphylla* Linn. of family Dioscoreaceae, commonly known as Five leaf yam^[5], which is widely used as a vegetable^[6] and to cure many health ailments^[7]. Due to its status as an Extra Pharmacopoeial Drug, it is imperative to study the preliminary physico-chemical and phyto-chemical properties, which aids in further researches. So, this article describes the Macroscopic, Microscopic, Organoleptic, Physico-chemical, Qualitative and Quantitative phytochemical analysis of *Bidali- Dioscorea pentaphylla* Linn.

Drug description

Taxonomical Classification:

Table 1 shows the Taxonomical Classification of *Bidali- Dioscorea pentaphylla* Linn.

Table 1: Taxonomical Classification of *Bidali- Dioscorea pentaphylla* Linn.^[8]

Class	Dicotyledonae
Order	Dioscoreales
Family	Dioscoreaceae
Genus	Dioscorea
Species	Pentaphylla

Macroscopic Description

Habitat:

Grown in degraded deciduous forests and sacred groves. It is also more common in foothills, the thickest parts and less common in plains and scrub jungles.^[9]

Distribution

Found throughout India- mainly in North- East India, Kerala, Andhra Pradesh, Maharashtra, and in Karnataka it is found in all states and mainly the Western Ghats, Odisha

Globally- India, Myanmar, Thailand, Indo-China, Pakistan, China, Malaysia, Sri Lanka, Australia, Papua New Guinea.^[9]

Morphology^[10]

Root: Tuber's oblong, very long, 1.5-1.8 m. **Stem:** Slender, twining, glabrous, prickly towards the base, often bulbiferous in the leaf-axils. **Leaves:** Alternate, 3-5-(rarely 7-) foliolate, glabrous or sparsely pubescent beneath; common petiole 2.5-6.3 cm. long; leaflets variable in size and shape, 5-12.5 by 2.5-5cm., elliptic-lanceolate, ovate, or obovate, acuminate, cuspidate or sub caudate, base usually acute; lateral leaflets oblique at the base; petiolules very short. **Inflorescence:** **Male Flowers-**Pale greenish, fragrant, in very slender shortly pedunculate racemes 2.5-3.8 cm. long, which are solitary or in fascicles along the hairy branches of a panicle 15-30cm. long; bracts 2.5 mm. long and as broad as long, membranous, often mottled with brown, broadly ovate, or almost semicircular, with a long slender acumen, glabrous. Perianth nearly 3 mm. across when spread out; segments often mottled with brown, ovate, subacute, sparsely pubescent, subequal; pedicels very short. Stamens 3 perfect; anthers subsessile; staminodes 3, minute. Pistilode 3-lobed. **Female flowers-** axillary pendulous pubescent spikes 5-15 cm. long. Capsules quadrately oblong, 2-2.5cm. long, usually retuse at both the ends, nearly glabrous or more or less pubescent, often apiculate. Seeds 1.3-2 cm. long (including the wing at the base); wing longer and broader than the oblique nucleus, thinly membranous. Figure 1 & 2 shows the same.

Useful part:

Tuber, Root, Leaves

Fig 1A

Fig 1B

Fig 1C

Fig 1: Identification of Bidali – *Dioscorea pentaphylla* Linn.Fig 2: Herbarium of Bidali- *Dioscorea pentaphylla* Linn.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Phase 1:

Collection of the Drug:

Bidali- Dioscorea pentaphylla Linn. tubers were collected from Devarayana Durga, Savana Durga (Tumkuru), Perdooru (Udupi), & Badamanavaratekaval (Bengaluru) in the month of September 2022.

Authentication of the Drug:

The collected drug sample was botanically identified and authenticated as *Bidali (Dioscorea pentaphylla* Linn.) by Senior Scientist (Botany), Dr. Shiva Manjunath M P., Department of Dravyaguna at Sri Sri College of Ayurvedic Science and Research, Bengaluru (Sample no.: DGMP S 041). The herbarium was prepared and was deposited at the Department of Dravyaguna, SSCASR.

Preparation of the Drug:

The tubers were washed thoroughly under running tap water, cut into small pieces, sun dried, powdered, and used for further analysis.

Phase 2:**Pharmacognostical evaluation:**

Macroscopic characterization, Microscopic analysis (Transverse section & Powder microscopy of tuber), Organoleptic evaluation, Physico-chemical evaluation, Preliminary Qualitative Phytochemical Analysis of Tuber were carried out in the Laboratory of Department of PG Studies in Dravyaguna, Sri Sri College of Ayurvedic Science and Research Bengaluru, Quantitative phytochemical analysis of *Bidali- Dioscorea pentaphylla* Linn. tuber was done at QA & QC Laboratory, Sri Veda Satva (Tattva) Private Limited, Bengaluru. All the analysis were carried out according to Standard protocol of Ayurvedic Pharmacopoeia of India.

RESULTS**Macroscopic Characteristics of fresh drug:**

Bidali - Dioscorea pentaphylla Linn. was a prickly climber having compound, penta-trifoliate leaves, and pedunculate racemes with white-green flowers. The tubers were long, tapered at the ends, and ran deep into the earth for 6-7 feet. The tubers were light brown in color and had secondary root growth.

Colourless exudate and longitudinal fibers were discernible while cutting the tubers. The pieces, which were whitish in color in the beginning, gradually turned reddish brown and dark brown during the course of sun drying, and a distinctive odor was noticed during this time and also while powdering the drug. Figure 3 & 4 represents the same.

Microscopic Characteristics:

The outline of T.S of tuber shows, The Cork, The Cortex and The Stellar region. **The cork:** The outer most layer of the tuber called the **Periderm**, formed by the accumulation of dead-undifferentiable cell. Angular cells with different size, which are closely packed with no intercellular space, for 2-3 inner layer of the Periderm forms **Cork Cambium**. **The cortex:** it is made up of circular parenchymatous cells of different sizes which are loosely arranged with intercellular spaces, showed the presence of Occicular calcium oxalate crystals, Mucilage and Starch. **The Stellar Region:** the elongated cells that are closely packed with each other forms the inner most layer of the Cortex and the outer most layer Stellar region called as **Endodermis**. A multilayered tissue with thin-walled cells which are compressed forms the **Pericycle**. **Vascular Bundle; Xylem:** The Xylem vessel is surrounded by the Xylem Fibers, and accompanied by the Tracheids and Xylem parenchyma, which are loosely arranged with more intercellular space. **Phloem:** The phloem is arranged beneath the xylem tissue, formed by a Companion cell, Phloem fiber (triangular on T.S), Sieve tube, and Phloem Parenchyma which are soft celled, arranged with more intercellular space. In between the two Vascular bundles, Angular cells with thick cell wall constitutes the **Sclerenchyma patch**. Figure 5 represents the T.S of *Bidali- Dioscorea pentaphylla* Linn.

Fig 5(A, B, C, D, E, F, G): Powder microscopy of *Bidali- Dioscorea pentaphylla* Linn.

5A- Periderm/Cork: Periderm and Phelloderm, 5B[Arrow]- Stellar Region: Endodermis, 5C[Arrow]-Stellar Region: Pericycle, 5D- Xylem vessel, 5E[Arrow]- Xylem Fiber, 5F[Arrow]-Trachieds, 5G[Box]- Pericycle

Organoleptic Characters of *Bidali- Dioscorea pentaphylla* Linn.

Table 2 shows the organoleptic characteristics of *Bidali- Dioscorea pentaphylla* Linn.

Table 2: Organoleptic characters of the *Bidali (Dioscorea pentaphylla* Linn.)

Organoleptic Characters	Fresh Drug	Dry Drug
Color	Dark brown	Brown
Texture	Rough	Coarse
Taste	Tingling sensation on tongue	Tingling sensation on tongue
Odor	Characteristic	Characteristic

Powder microscopy:

The Bundle of tracheids, Fragments of Parenchyma tissue, Xylem fiber, Trachea, Bundle of Vascular tissue, Cork Cell, Occicular Calcium Oxalate Crystal, Starch, Lipid and Mucilage were observed in powder microscopy of *Bidali- Dioscorea pentaphylla* Linn. Figure 6 represents the powder microscopy of *Bidali-Dioscorea pentaphylla* Linn.

Physico-chemical Analysis:

Table 3 enumerates the Physico-chemical analysis of *Bidali- Dioscorea pentaphylla* Linn.

Table 3: Physico-chemical analysis of *Bidali -Dioscorea pentaphylla* Linn.

Sl.no	Parameter	Values
1.	Loss on drying	88.69%
2.	Total ash	8.91%
3.	Acid-insoluble ash	1.980%
4.	Water soluble extractive	4.4%
5.	Alcohol soluble extractive	2.2%

Phytochemical evaluation:**Qualitative analysis**

Table 4 shows the Phytochemical analysis of *Bidali- Dioscorea pentaphylla* Linn.

Table 4: Phytochemical analysis of *Bidali (Dioscorea pentaphylla)* Linn.)

Sl no	Test for	Test	Results		
			Aqueous Extract	Alcoholic Extract	Hydro alcoholic Extract
1	Alkaloids	Mayer's test	-	-	-
		Wagner's test	-	-	-
		Dragendroff's test	+	+	+
2	Carbohydrates	Molisch's test	+	+	+
		Starch test	-	-	-
		Fehling's test	-	-	+
		Benedict's	+	+	+
3	Proteins	Biuret's test	-	-	-
		Millan's test	+	-	-
		Ninhydrin test	+	-	-
4	Tannins	Gelatin test	+	+	+
5	Phenols	Ferric chloride test	+	+	+
		Lead acetate test	+	-	-
6	Saponins	Foam test	+	+	+
7	Fixed oils	Stain test	+	+	+
8	Triterpenoids	Lieberman's test	-	-	-
9	Steroids	Salkowski's test	+	+	+
		Lieberman's	-	+	+
10	Flavonoids	Lead acetate test	+	+	+
		Aq. NaOH solution test	-	-	-
		Conc. H ₂ SO ₄ test	+	+	+
		lead acetate test	+	+	+

The above table contains the details of qualitative tests for Phytochemicals in the Aqueous, Alcoholic and Hydro-alcoholic extracts if *Bidali- Dioscorea pentaphylla* Linn.

Quantification of phytochemicals

Table 5 describes the Quantification of Phytochemicals of *Bidali - Dioscorea pentaphylla* Linn.

Table 5: Quantification of Phytochemicals of *Bidali (Dioscorea pentaphylla)* Linn.) (Annexure Fig.10).

Sl no	Phytochemical constituent	Quantification (in %)
1	Alkaloids	0.47
2	Flavones	4.25
3	Saponins	3.508
4	Tannins	0.4157

The above table shows the quantity (in %) of Phytochemicals in *Bidali- Dioscorea pentaphylla* Linn. (Where powdered drug was used for the quantification).

DISCUSSION

Discussion on macroscopic identification of *Bidali*:

In Sushruta Samhita, the commentator Acharya Dalhana describes two types of *Vidari*- as one with “*Hasti PadavatKanda*” ~ the plant with tuber resembling the foot of an Elephant and the other with “*Dirgha Kanda*” ~ the plant with elongated tubers.^[2] In another context, the word *Bidali* / *Virali* is used synonymously to the drug *Vidari*.^[11] Many Authors, and Stalwarts of this era opine that, *Dioscorea pentaphylla* Linn. as the one with elongated tubers as source of *Bidali*.^[3,4]

Many synonyms attributing to *Bidali*'s morphological features are available throughout the classics and lexicons of Ayurveda such as: *Dirghakanda*^[2] (*Dirgha*-elongated, *Kanda*-tuber)- the plant with elongated tubers, *Ksheeravalli*^[3] (*Ksheera*-Exudate, *Valli*-Climber)- the twining climber with the latex, *Payasvini*^[3]- the tuber yielding latex, *Shuklakanda*^[12,13] (*Shukla*-White, *Kanda*- Tuber)- the plant with white tubers, *Kandavalli*^[14,15] (*Kanda*-tuber, *Valli*- climber)- the climber with tuber, *Shukla*^[16] (white), *Ksheerashukla*^[3] (*Ksheera*-Milk, *Shukla*- White)- the tuber with white color as that of milk. These given synonyms of *Bidali* and external morphology of *Dioscorea pentaphylla* Linn., very well correlate, it is taken as a source of *Bidali*, and a variety of *Vidari*.

Discussion on Pharmacognosy of *Bidali*:

To know the genuinity and identity of give drug sample the powder microscopy is carried out. The loss on drying, which serves as a barometer for the sample's economic worth, stability, and storage practices, can be used to assess the sample's moisture content. Ash values are employed to assess both the quality and purity of crude drugs. It implies the presence of many particles, such as carbonate, oxalate, and silicate. An indication of contamination with earthy material is the acid-insoluble ash, which is largely silica-containing. The assessment of extractive values determines the concentration of the active components in each quantity of plant material after extraction with a particular solvent. Any crude drugs can be extracted with a particular solvent to get a mixture of phytoconstituents. These phytoconstituents are constructed variably depending on the drug and the solvent used. It also shows whether the crude drug has been exhausted.^[17]

While cutting the tubers of *Bidali*- *Dioscorea pentaphylla* Linn., colorless exudate was seen and when they came into contact with skin, it caused irritations such as erythema, itching, pricking, and burning sensation, which is substantiated by the presence of Mucilage and Occular Calcium Oxalate Crystals in powder microscopy.

In the current study, Loss on Drying was 88.69% Total Ash was 8.9%, Acid insoluble ash was 1.9%, Water Soluble extractive value was 4.4% and Alcohol Soluble extractive was 2.2%. as this drug is not mentioned in Ayurvedic Pharmacopoeia of India, it can be taken up for further studies.

The Qualitative preliminary phytochemical analysis of *Bidali* (*Dioscorea pentaphylla* Linn.) tuber aqueous, alcoholic, and hydro-alcoholic extracts showed the presence of Alkaloids, Steroids, Carbohydrates, Starch, Protein, Tannins, Phenols, Flavonoids, Saponins, and that were consistent with the literature. On Quantification of secondary metabolites, it showed 4.25% of Flavones, 3.508% of Saponins, 0.47% of Alkaloids and 0.4157% of Tannins.

Due to its status as an extra-pharmacopoeial drugs in Ayurveda, studies on its pharmacognosy, corresponding to therapeutical applications listed in the classics of Ayurveda are of great importance for research regarding phytotherapy.

CONCLUSION

It can be speculated that *Dioscorea pentaphylla* Linn is a source of *Bidali* which is a variant of *Vidari* based on the provided synonyms for *Bidali* and its external morphology. *Bidali*- *Dioscorea pentaphylla* Linn. tubers were analyzed for its Pharmacognostical profile. The obtained results were compared with the available literature. The preliminary qualitative phytochemical analysis revealed the presence of alkaloids, steroids, carbohydrates, Starch, Protein, tannins, phenols, flavonoids, saponins. On quantitative phytochemical analysis showed the presence of Flavones and Saponins in higher concentration indicating the therapeutic probabilities, which allows for further exploration.

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Competing Interest

There is no any conflict of interest.

ABBREVIATIONS

Aq. NaOH - Aqueous Sodium Hydroxide
Conc. H₂SO₄ - Concentrated Sulphuric Acid

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